

Newly Diagnosed Diabetic Retinopathy in Know Type 2 Diabetic PatientsArshad Dhukka¹, Amrit Kejriwal², Mohammad Awais Farooqui³¹Junior Resident, Department of General Medicine, MGM Medical College, Kamothe²Professor, Department of General Medicine, MGM Medical College, Kamothe³Senior resident, Department of Cardiology, MGM Medical College, Kamothe

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Abstract:

Background: Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a significant microvascular complication of type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), leading to vision impairment if untreated. With diabetes prevalence rising globally, including India, early detection and management of DR are critical to prevent severe outcomes. This study aims to evaluate the prevalence of newly diagnosed DR among T2DM patients and its association with disease duration and glycemic control.

Methods: A cross-sectional observational study was conducted over one month, involving 100 T2DM patients. Data collected included demographic details, diabetes duration, treatment regimens, and HbA1c levels. Comprehensive dilated eye exams assessed DR presence and severity.

Results: The prevalence of DR was 37%. Among affected patients, 40.54% had mild non-proliferative retinopathy, 32.43% had moderate non-proliferative retinopathy, 18.92% had severe non-proliferative retinopathy, and 8.11% had proliferative retinopathy. Significant associations were found between DR and longer diabetes duration ($p < 0.001$) and higher HbA1c levels ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusion: The high prevalence of DR among T2DM patients highlights the need for regular eye screening. Effective glycemic control and early detection are essential to prevent severe DR and associated visual impairment.

Keywords: Diabetic Retinopathy, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, Glycemic Control, Prevalence, Eye Screening.

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Introduction

Diabetic retinopathy (DR) is a microvascular complication associated with diabetes mellitus, which can lead to significant visual impairment and blindness if not managed appropriately. It occurs due to damage to the retinal blood vessels caused by chronic hyperglycemia. This damage can lead to leakage of blood and other fluids, causing the macular edema and resulting in cloudy or blurred vision. Over time, the condition can progress to proliferative diabetic retinopathy, where abnormal blood vessels grow on the retina, leading to severe vision problems.

Prevalence and Burden

The prevalence of diabetes has surged dramatically over recent decades, with the number of affected individuals rising from 108 million in 1980 to 422 million in 2014. This increase has been more pronounced in low- and middle-income countries compared to high-income nations. Diabetes is a significant contributor to severe health complications, including blindness, kidney failure, heart attacks, stroke, and lower limb amputation. Between 2000 and 2019, diabetes mortality rates in-

creased by 3%, with diabetes and associated kidney disease accounting for an estimated 2 million deaths in 2019. [1] Diabetes mellitus and diabetic retinopathy (DR) present significant global public health challenges. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF), recently labeled diabetes as a "pandemic of unprecedented magnitude," in conjunction with the release of the latest epidemiologic estimates of the global disease burden. [3] The IDF's latest report indicates that 10.5% of the world's adult population, or over 1 in 10 individuals, currently live with diabetes, amounting to more than half a billion people. Projections suggest that this number will rise sharply, reaching almost 800 million by 2045. Importantly, this disease burden affects countries worldwide, regardless of their income and development status. While non-communicable diseases, including diabetes, were traditionally seen as issues primarily for high-income, developed countries, there are now more individuals with diabetes in developing countries than in developed ones. [4] India, which is home to the second-largest number of people with diabetes in the world, faces

a significant burden from diabetic complications, including DR. A recent study aimed to estimate the national and subnational prevalence of DR and vision-threatening diabetic retinopathy (VTDR) in India, revealing that the condition is highly prevalent and often underdiagnosed. [5,6] The study emphasized the need for improved screening and management strategies to address this growing public health issue. [7,8]

Type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) is the most common form of diabetes and is characterized by insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency. The increasing prevalence of T2DM globally has been associated with a corresponding rise in the incidence of diabetic complications, including DR. In India, the prevalence of diabetes has increased by 64.3% from 1990 to 2016, reflecting a significant public health challenge. [9]

Individuals with diabetes need to undergo regular eye exams to monitor and manage this condition. DR manifests in two main stages: Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR) and Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR). NPDR, the early stage, involves leaky blood vessels causing retinal swelling, leading to blurred vision. PDR, the more advanced stage, is characterized by the growth of new, fragile blood vessels that can bleed into the vitreous, potentially causing severe vision impairment. Diagnosing DR involves dilated eye exams, optical coherence tomography (OCT), and fluorescein angiography. Treatments include blood sugar control, anti-VEGF medication, laser surgery, and vitrectomy. This study aims to elucidate the prevalence, diagnosis, and treatment of diabetic retinopathy, emphasizing the importance of early detection and management to prevent vision loss. [10]

Preventive measures such as a healthy diet; regular physical activity, maintaining a normal body weight, and avoiding tobacco use are effective in delaying or preventing the onset of type 2 diabetes. Additionally, diabetes management through diet, physical activity, medication, and regular screening and treatment for complications can prevent or delay its severe consequences. [3,4]

Aim & Objectives:

The objectives of this study are:

1. To determine the prevalence of diabetic retinopathy in patients diagnosed with Diabetes Mellitus.
2. To analyze the relation between diabetic retinopathy and the total duration of Diabetes.
3. To assess the relation between glycemic control and the development of Diabetic Retinopathy.

Study Design

Type: Cross-sectional observational study conducted for a duration of 1 month with a sample Size of 100 patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Adults aged 18 and older up to 60 years of age
- Patients diagnosed with type 2 diabetes
- Able to provide informed consent

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients with other retinal diseases not related to diabetes
- Patients who have undergone retinal surgery, pan-retinal photocoagulation, focal & grid photocoagulation anti VEGF therapy
- Patients with a pre-existing diagnosis of diabetic retinopathy

Sampling Method: Convenience sampling from patients attending Medicine and Diabetes OPD

Data Collection

Demographic Information: Age, Gender, Duration of diabetes, Treatment regimen (insulin, oral hypoglycemic, combination therapy)

Clinical Assessment:

- HbA1c levels to measure the glycemic control
- Screening for diabetic retinopathy was conducted through a comprehensive dilated eye examination. Pupil dilation was achieved using mydriatic drops either tropicamide 1% or phenylephrine 2.5%. An ophthalmoscope (Welch Allyn 250) was then used to examine the retina, macula, optic disc, and retinal blood vessels for signs of diabetic retinopathy, including microaneurysms, hemorrhages, hard exudates, and neovascularization.

Outcome Measures:

- Presence of diabetic retinopathy (non-proliferative or proliferative).
- HbA1c levels.

Patient Recruitment:

- Eligible patients were identified during their routine visits to the Medicine OPD and diabetes clinic.
- Informed consent was obtained from each participant.

Data Collection:

- Demographic and clinical data were recorded.
- HbA1c levels were measured using Diabetes control and complication trial (DCCT) and National Glycohemoglobin Standardization Programme (NGSP) recommend Ion exchange HPLC method.

- Detailed eye examinations, including retinal imaging, were conducted to detect and classify diabetic retinopathy.

Classification of Diabetic Retinopathy:

1. No Diabetic Retinopathy

- **Definition:** No visible signs of diabetic retinopathy are present on retinal examination.
- **Key Findings:** Absence of microaneurysms, hemorrhages, hard exudates, or neovascularization.

2. Non-Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (NPDR)

Mild NPDR:

- **Definition:** Early stage of DR with minimal retinal changes.
- **Key Findings:** Presence of at least one microaneurysm; possible mild retinal hemorrhages.

Moderate NPDR:

- **Definition:** Moderate progression of retinal changes without severe visual impairment.
- **Key Findings:** Increased number of microaneurysms and retinal hemorrhages, presence of hard exudates, and venous beading.

Severe NPDR:

- **Definition:** Advanced stage of NPDR with significant risk of progression to proliferative DR.
- **Key Findings:** Any one of the following criteria:
 - More than 20 intraretinal hemorrhages in each of the four quadrants.
 - Venous beading in two or more quadrants.
 - Prominent intraretinal microvascular abnormalities (IRMA) in at least one quadrant.

3. Proliferative Diabetic Retinopathy (PDR)

- **Definition:** Advanced stage of DR characterized by neovascularization, which can lead to severe vision loss.
- **Key Findings:**
 - Neovascularization on the retina, optic disc, or elsewhere in the eye.
 - Vitreous or preretinal hemorrhages.

- Fibrous tissue proliferation leading to tractional retinal detachment.

4. Diabetic Macular Edema (DME)

- **Definition:** Swelling or thickening of the macula due to fluid accumulation from leaking blood vessels, which can occur at any stage of DR.
- **Key Findings:**
 - Retinal thickening within two disc diameters of the center of the macula.
 - Hard exudates within two disc diameters of the center of the macula, if associated with adjacent retinal thickening.

Statistical Analysis

1. **Prevalence of Diabetic Retinopathy:** The overall prevalence was calculated by dividing the number of patients with diabetic retinopathy by the total number of patients.
2. **Associational Analysis:**
 - **Duration of Diabetes:** Regression analysis was performed between the duration of diabetes and the presence of diabetic retinopathy. In addition, the point-biserial correlation analysis was also performed for additional evidence of association.
 - **Severity of Diabetes (HbA1c Levels):** The relationship between HbA1c levels and the presence and severity of diabetic retinopathy was analyzed.
 - Logistic regression was used to determine the association between HbA1c levels and the risk of developing diabetic retinopathy.

3. Statistical Software: Statistical analyses were conducted using Statistical Package for Social Sciences V 20.0 (IBM, Inc. USA) SPSS.

Ethical Considerations

- **Informed Consent:** Written informed consent was obtained from all participants.
- **Confidentiality:** Patient data were anonymized and stored securely.
- **Ethical Approval:** Approval was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) before commencing the study.

Results:

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants (N=100)

Characteristic	Total (n=100)
Age (years)	55.32 (12.48)
Gender - Male	55 (55.00%)
Gender - Female	45 (45.00%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	12.49 (7.81)
Treatment Regimen	
- Oral Hypoglycemics	76 (76.00%)
- Insulin	13 (13.00%)
- Combination Therapy	11 (11.00%)

The study included 100 participants with an average age of 55.32 years (SD = 12.48).

The gender distribution comprised 55 males (55.00%) and 45 females (45.00%). On average,

participants had been diagnosed with diabetes for 12.49 years (SD = 7.81). Regarding treatment regimens, 76 participants (76.00%) were on oral hypoglycemics, 13 (13.00%) were on insulin, and 11 (11.00%) were on combination therapy.

Table 2: Prevalence of Diabetic Retinopathy among Study Participants

Diabetic Retinopathy	n (%)
Present	37 (37.00%)
Absent	63 (63.00%)

The overall prevalence of diabetic retinopathy among the participants was found to be 37%, with 37 patients having retinopathy and 63 patients not having retinopathy.

Table 3: Severity of Diabetic Retinopathy

Severity Level	Total (n=37)
Mild Non-Proliferative	15 (40.54%)
Moderate Non-Proliferative	12 (32.43%)
Severe Non-Proliferative	7 (18.92%)
Proliferative	3 (8.11%)

Among the 37 patients with diabetic retinopathy, 40.54% had mild non-proliferative retinopathy, 32.43% had moderate non-proliferative retinopathy, 18.92% had severe non-proliferative retinopathy, and 8.11% had proliferative retinopathy.

Table 4: Comparison of Demographic Characteristics with Presence of Diabetic Retinopathy

Characteristic	Diabetic Retinopathy (n=37)	No Diabetic Retinopathy (n=63)	p-Value
Age (years)	57.2 (12.4)	53.8 (13.1)	0.223
Gender - Male	21 (56.76%)	34 (53.97%)	0.758
Gender - Female	16 (43.24%)	29 (46.03%)	0.758
Duration of Diabetes (years)	15.2 (7.0)	10.1 (5.5)	<0.001
Treatment Regimen			
- Oral Hypoglycemics	32 (86.48%)	44 (69.84%)	0.195
- Insulin	6 (16.22%)	7 (11.12%)	0.378
- Combination Therapy	3 (8.11%)	8 (12.70%)	0.458

The mean age of patients with diabetic retinopathy was 57.2 years (SD = 12.4), compared to 53.8 years (SD = 13.1) for those without retinopathy (p = 0.223). The duration of diabetes was significantly longer in patients with retinopathy (15.2 years, SD

= 7.0) compared to those without (10.1 years, SD = 5.5), with a p-value of <0.001.

No significant differences were observed in gender distribution or treatment regimens between the two groups.

Table 5: Logistic Regression Analysis of Factors Associated with Diabetic Retinopathy

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-Value
Duration of Diabetes (years)	1.12	1.06 - 1.18	< 0.001
HbA1c Levels	1.25	1.10 - 1.42	0.001
Age (years)	1.02	0.98 - 1.05	0.223
Gender (Male)	1.15	0.50 - 2.65	0.758
Insulin Use	1.58	0.79 - 3.16	0.195
Oral Hypoglycemics	0.63	0.23 - 1.75	0.378
Combination Therapy	0.60	0.15 - 2.39	0.458

The logistic regression analysis revealed that both the duration of diabetes (OR = 1.12, 95% CI: 1.06 - 1.18, p < 0.001) and HbA1c levels (OR = 1.25, 95% CI: 1.10 - 1.42, p = 0.001) were significant predictors of diabetic retinopathy. Age and gender were not significantly associated with the presence of retinopathy.

Discussion

This study highlights the significant prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) among known type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM) patients. With an overall prevalence of 37%, this aligns with global data indicating high rates of DR among diabetic populations. This prevalence underscores the critical need for regular eye screenings in diabetic patients to

detect DR early and prevent severe visual impairment.

Recent studies in India have revealed various prevalence rates for diabetic retinopathy: 21.7% on a nationwide scale, 12.27% in central India, and 34.06% in North India. An overall study in India found a prevalence of 15%, while in Pune, it was 14.3%. Among Singapore Indians, a six-year study reported an incidence of 21.89% and a progression rate of 33.45%. Although direct comparisons between studies are challenging due to differences in methodologies, geographic regions, diagnostic criteria, and population characteristics, these rates are significant. The findings are consistent with previous studies, showing a higher prevalence of non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR) compared to proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), similar to observations made in South India. [11,12,13]

A slightly higher prevalence was recorded in a study conducted by Stia S et al where approximately 42.5% of the patients tested positive for diabetic retinopathy. Among these, 29.41% had mild non-proliferative diabetic retinopathy (NPDR), 41.18% had moderate NPDR, and 29.41% had diabetic maculopathy. There were no cases of severe NPDR or proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) detected. [14] In another study, 52.07% of patients with Type 2 diabetes mellitus (DM) for over 10 years had diabetic retinopathy, while 13.07% of patients with Type 2 DM for more than 5 years had the condition. [15]

The study identified several key risk factors for the development of DR. Duration of diabetes emerged as a significant predictor. This is consistent with existing literature that has long established the duration of diabetes as a primary risk factor for DR. Higher HbA1c levels were also significantly associated with DR, reinforcing the importance of glycemic control in preventing microvascular complications. The study's logistic regression analysis indicated that each one-unit increase in HbA1c levels increased the risk of DR by 1.25 times, emphasizing the need for stringent blood sugar management.

In a study conducted by Gadkari SS et al the prevalence was higher among males ($P = 0.007$), diabetics for more than 5 years ($P = 0.001$), individuals over 40 years old ($P = 0.01$), insulin users ($P = 0.001$), and those with a history of vascular accidents ($P = 0.0014$). Notably, 22.18% of patients diagnosed with DR had a vision of 6/18 or better in their worse eye. [11] Similar to the present study, another one demonstrated a significantly higher prevalence of diabetic retinopathy with increasing age (OR: 2.367) and longer duration of diabetes (OR: 3.318). [11] In the Wisconsin epidemiological study, the prevalence of DR ranged from 28.8% in

individuals with diabetes for less than 5 years to 77.8% in those with diabetes for 15 or more years. The prevalence ranged from 9.23% in newly diagnosed diabetics (less than 6 months) to 35.12% in those with diabetes for over 5 years. Contrary to our results males (OR: 1.212) were more affected in this study. Gender bias and social barriers to treatment are recognized issues that influence access to screening and treatment. [16]

In a similar study conducted in south India the prevalence of DR, adjusted for age and gender, was 0.05% (95% CI 0.04 to 0.06%) in rural areas and 1.03% (95% CI 0.89 to 1.12%) in urban areas. The overall adjusted prevalence of DR, accounting for age, gender, and cluster, was 0.74% (95% CI 0.66 to 0.83%). Among those with DM, 12.2% (95% CI 10.4 to 14.1%) were found to have diabetic retinopathy. [17]

Glycemic control, as indicated by plasma glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C) levels, was assessed in another similar study. Patients with HbA1C levels higher than 8.95 ± 2.14 demonstrated a greater prevalence of diabetic retinopathy (DR) compared to those with lower HbA1C values, indicative of more optimal glycemic control. There was a statistically significant positive correlation between higher HbA1C levels and retinopathy, with a P -value < 0.0001 . Patients with proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR) had an average HbA1C level of 10.56 ± 2.15 . The study also explored the relationship between treatment regimens and DR prevalence. Patients on insulin had a higher prevalence of DR compared to those on oral hypoglycemics or combination therapy. This might reflect more advanced or poorly controlled diabetes in patients requiring insulin, rather than insulin use per se causing DR. It suggests that patients with more severe diabetes are at greater risk for DR, necessitating more vigilant monitoring and possibly more aggressive treatment strategies.

The findings from this study have several implications for clinical practice. Firstly, the high prevalence of DR in known T2DM patients supports the need for regular retinal screening as part of routine diabetes care. Early detection of DR through regular eye examinations can prevent progression to more severe stages of the disease, such as proliferative diabetic retinopathy (PDR), which can lead to significant vision loss.

Moreover, the strong association between glycemic control and DR underscores the importance of maintaining optimal blood sugar levels to mitigate the risk of developing DR. This necessitates a comprehensive diabetes management plan that includes lifestyle modifications, regular monitoring of blood glucose levels, and appropriate pharmacologic interventions. The studies (Berrabeh et al., 2023) (Wang et al., 2020) (Romero-Aroca et al.,

2017) (Cui et al., 2019) reveal key insights into diabetic retinopathy prevalence and risk factors. Berrabeh et al. (Berrabeh et al., 2023) explored risk factors in a Type 1 Diabetes population, while Wang et al. (Wang et al., 2020) compared early- and late-onset diabetes' impact on DR and macular edema prevalence.

Romero-Aroca et al. (Romero-Aroca et al., 2017) focused on DR incidence differences over nine years between Type 1 and Type 2 diabetes. Lastly, Cui et al. (Cui et al., 2019) investigated DR prevalence and associated risks in a rural Chinese population, highlighting the importance of awareness and early detection, particularly in those with longer diabetes duration and hyperglycemia. [19-22]

Limitations and Future Research: This study's cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality between the identified risk factors and DR. Longitudinal studies are needed to confirm these associations and to understand the temporal relationship between diabetes management and DR progression. Additionally, the study's sample size, though adequate for preliminary findings, would benefit from larger, more diverse populations to enhance the generalizability of the results.

Future research should also investigate the effectiveness of different screening intervals and the impact of various diabetes management strategies on the progression of DR. Understanding the genetic and molecular mechanisms underlying DR could lead to more targeted therapies and preventative measures.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the high prevalence of diabetic retinopathy among patients with known T2DM in this study highlights the urgent need for regular screening and effective diabetes management to prevent this debilitating complication. Age, duration of diabetes, and glycemic control are significant risk factors for DR, emphasizing the importance of comprehensive diabetes care. Addressing these factors through early intervention and continuous monitoring can significantly reduce the burden of DR and improve the quality of life for diabetic patients.

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